

Central American tree frogs of the genus *Smilisca* in nature and captivity

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INTRODUCTION

Tree frogs of the genus *Smilisca* are not among the most well-known terrarium animals. This is somewhat unfortunate, since these hardy, active and easy-to-breed amphibians can give even novice tree frog keepers years of pleasure. In this article I would like to introduce these frogs and allow the reader a little peek into the life of two common species: *Smilisca baudinii* and *Smilisca phaeota*.

THE GENUS *SMILISCA*

The genus *Smilisca* ranges from the extreme southern USA to Ecuador and Colombia. However, most species inhabit the lowlands of Mexico and Central America, and in this part of the world they are often hard to miss. On rainy nights early in the wet season many species of male tree frogs loudly declare their love to their respective females and tell other males to stay away. However, *Smilisca* species - in particular the ones that breed in temporary pools - are often the first ones to start calling and are usually found in larger numbers, making them hard to miss. Due to their abundance in some areas, including secondary growth around human settlements, these frogs are sometimes accidentally packaged and shipped with bananas or other goods from Central America. On occasion I have seen *Smilisca baudinii* and *Smilisca phaeota* for sale in pet stores.

Drab Tree Frog (*Smilisca sordida*), male.
Photo: T. Leenders

Drab Tree Frog (*Smilisca sordida*), female.
Photo: T. Leenders

In general appearance, the species of *Smilisca* are 'typical' tree frogs, with enlarged adhesive disks on their fingers and toes, a flattened body, large, bulging eyes, and extensive skin-like webbing on their hands and feet. They resemble tree frogs of the genus *Hyla*, and were placed in that genus until the early 80s. However, based on small differences in the jaw musculature, *Smilisca* was placed in a separate taxon (SAVAGE & VILLA, 1986). Naturally, this is not a very useful characteristic to distinguish these genera in the field, but luckily there is an easier way: male *Smilisca* possess a paired subgular vocal sac, while in male *Hyla* the vocal sac is always single. A few species of *Hyla*, such as *Hyla pseudopuma*, have a vocal sac that appears pseudo-paired (because of a median constriction down the centre of the throat).

The presence of a vocal sac is also the easiest way to distinguish males and females. Even when the vocal sac is not extended, a dark throat identifies the males.

The frogs of the genus *Smilisca* are of medium to large size, the maximum snout-vent length of a female *Smilisca baudinii* is 96 mm, making them one of the largest tree frogs in Central America. The males in *Smilisca* are generally much smaller than the females.

The coloration of these tree frogs is highly variable and can change with the physical condition of each individual or with atmospheric changes. However, their usual coloration is usually some shade of brown or green, sometimes with a pattern of irregular dark blotches on the back.

THE SPECIES

Drab Tree Frog (*Smilisca sordida*), male.

Photo: T. Leenders

This relatively small genus is comprised of six species: *Smilisca baudinii*, *Smilisca cyanosticta*, *Smilisca phaeota*, *Smilisca puma*, *Smilisca sila*, and *Smilisca sordida* (DUELLMAN, 1970). Those most commonly seen are *S. baudinii* and *S. phaeota*, since these frogs are among the few species of amphibians that prefer secondary habitats and are often found near human settlements. They breed in temporary rain puddles, ponds, ditches, and other relatively shallow bodies of stagnant water. This reproductive strategy is shared with *S.*

cyanosticta and *S. puma*. The latter two species are relatively uncommon, and prefer less disturbed habitat in isolated premontane areas. *Smilisca baudinii* and *S. phaeota*, on the other hand, are widespread throughout the lowlands of Central America.

The remaining two species, *S. sila* and *S. sordida*, are stream-breeders. Where the other species are found sleeping on leaves or under tree bark during the day, individual *S. sila* and *S. sordida* are seen on rocks in low gradient, rocky rivers. Often the frogs are perched in an exposed spot, subject to direct sunlight.

Since stream-breeding frogs live in a relatively noisy habitat that is stretched out over a long distance, these frogs are much harder to hear and find than their temporary pool-breeding congeners which gather in numbers around a small pool on suitable nights. For example, a breeding congregation of more than 45,000 *S. baudinii* recorded from a pond in Veracruz, Mexico, will be a lot easier to find than a single male *S. sordida*, calling over the sound of a rushing mountain stream in the rainforest of Costa Rica. This relative rarity is also reflected in our knowledge of these frogs and not much is known about the biology of the rarer species.

It would be beyond the scope of this article to describe all these species in detail. I would therefore like to limit the remainder of this article to a brief description of *S. baudinii* and *S. phaeota* - the two species that one would most likely encounter in the wild and that are easiest to maintain in captivity.

Mexican Tree Frog (*Smilisca baudinii*).

Photo: T. Leenders

SMILISCA BAUDINII, THE MEXICAN TREE FROG

Mexican Tree Frog (*Smilisca baudinii*).

Photo: T. Leenders

In spite of its common name, *S. baudinii* is found far beyond the Mexican border. Its distribution range extends from southern Texas south through the lowlands of Central America to Costa Rica. *Smilisca baudinii* also occurs on some islands in the Caribbean, such as the islands off the coast of the Yucatán Peninsula and the Bay Islands.

Smilisca baudinii is a large, robust frog: males attain a length of 76 mm, females grow even larger and can reach a maximum size of well over 90 mm. This species is distinguished from all other Central American tree frogs by the combination of the following characteristics: *S. baudinii* has a prominent row of warts along the lower arm and a dark brown bar that extends from below each eye to the upper lip. Adjacent

to this bar is a light green, grey, or cream-coloured spot, but this feature is sometimes hard to see in lighter coloured frogs.

Smilisca baudinii is highly variable in colour and pattern; the upper surfaces can be a shade of green, tan, or brown, with a pattern of dark, irregular blotches. In breeding males, the area on the throat where the vocal sac is located is grey; the remaining ventral surfaces are white to creamy yellow. The short-snouted head bears a dark, mask-like eye stripe that extends backward onto the shoulder area. The eardrums are distinctly visible, and the eye has a horizontal pupil with a bronze or silver iris. As in *S. phaeota*, dark transverse bars mark the dorsal surfaces of the hind limbs, although in *S. baudinii* there is no distinct white stripe running along the outer edge of the leg and foot.

The mating call of these frogs, a series of short "wonk-wonk-wonk" notes, is commonly heard on rainy nights near any type of temporary pond within the species' distribution range. *Smilisca baudinii* usually call in duets, with two males calling in an alternating fashion. Calling males are usually seen on bushes or small trees near the water's edge, and they may be separated by only a few centimetres. The call sequence of one duet may be picked up quickly by other vocalising individuals, and the resulting chorus may produce a deafening ruckus. Although the intensity of the calls increases gradually as more individuals join a chorus, an entire chorus frequently stops abruptly. After a short interval in which all frogs are silent, one duet will initiate the next massive sing-along (LEENDERS, 2001).

SMILISCA PHAEOTA, THE MASKED TREE FROG

The silvery white stripe on the upper lip and a dark, mask-like stripe that starts near the nostril will distinguish *S. phaeota* from all other Central American tree frogs. This stripe runs along both sides of the head to somewhere near the insertion of the arms, encompassing the eye and eardrum, and is the obvious origin of the common name 'masked tree frog'. Many individuals also sport a green spot on each side of the head between the dark mask and the lip.

Masked Tree Frog (*Smilisca phaeota*).

Photo: T. Leenders

Rio Molinete in Costa Rica. Home to both *Smilisca sordida* (in the river) and *Smilisca phaeota* (in the shallow water-filled depressions along the riverbanks).

Photo: T. Leenders

This species is capable of changing colour, and its upper surfaces can be either tan or green; they are usually tan during the day and green at night. The back is variably patterned with olive-green or brown blotches. On the top of the head, a dark bar connecting the eyes is nearly always present. The ventral surfaces are creamy white, although in males the area of the throat where the vocal sac sits is sometimes yellowish, cream, or grey. The hind limbs are adorned with both alternating light and dark transverse bands and a distinct white stripe that runs along the outer edge of the leg and foot. Adult females of this large species may reach 78 mm; males are

considerably smaller with a maximum size of 65 mm.

Smilisca phaeota occurs in lowland rainforests from northern Nicaragua to northern Colombia.

Like all other tree frogs, *S. phaeota* is mostly active during the night. Individuals spend the day sleeping on the upper surface of large leaves, but they have also been found on the top of large tree ferns or in rolled-up banana leaves. On two occasions, however, males of this species were found actively climbing on vegetation in the spray zone of a large waterfall in broad daylight. At nightfall on rainy nights, males begin producing their calls - a surprisingly loud and harsh "wrauk", attempting to persuade a female to join them. Their calls have been likened to the roar of a bull, and their Spanish common name 'Torito' (little bull) attests to that. Masked tree frogs call from the water surface of small rain pools (e.g., drainage ditches or water-filled tire tracks) that are shaded by trees during the day (LEENDERS, 2001).

REPRODUCTIVE BEHAVIOUR IN NATURE

Since both *S. baudinii* and *S. phaeota* breed in temporary ponds, the peak of their breeding season is during the rainy season when these breeding sites are abundant and the chance of them drying out is minimal. This is different for the stream-breeding *Smilisca*, which breed during the dry season when the water level in streams is low and there is less of a risk that their eggs or offspring will wash away during a flood.

The eggs of *S. baudinii*, *S. phaeota*, and other pond-breeding *Smilisca* are laid in a thin layer floating on the water surface. In *S. phaeota*, the eggs are in small clumps, whereas *S. baudinii* produces a continuous layer. The eggs hatch rapidly, often within a day. The larval development of these species is extremely fast, in comparison with other frogs and toads, since their environment is very unstable. Under tropical conditions even the shaded rain puddles used by *Smilisca* can evaporate completely if it fails to rain for a day or two, which will kill the tadpoles. Laboratory studies with tadpoles of *S. phaeota* revealed that these larvae can survive up to 24 hours out of the water, undoubtedly an adaptation to their risky reproductive strategy (VALERIO, 1971).

Masked Tree Frog (*Smilisca phaeota*), male. Note the differently coloured throat.

Photo: T. Leenders

Tadpoles of *S. baudinii* and *S. phaeota* complete metamorphosis and leave their birth pools roughly one month after hatching.

IN CAPTIVITY

Both *S. baudinii* and *S. phaeota* can be kept in a 'standard' rainforest terrarium with lots of strong plants and a relatively high humidity. The air temperature should be maintained at approximately 25-26°C during the day, and a few degrees cooler at night. These frogs inhabit areas where the night-time temperature sometimes plummets to 14-15°C, and are thus fairly tolerant of low temperatures.

The terrarium should not be too small; at least 100x50x100 cm (lxwxh) because *S. baudinii* can jump impressively when startled, and the frogs can easily hurt themselves if there is not enough room to move around. Many tree frogs like to sleep on large leaves or hidden away inside the corona of leaves of a bromeliad. Broad-leaved plants and large enough bromeliads also require some space to develop fully. Additionally, a shallow basin filled to a depth of approximately 10 cm with clean water should be present during the breeding season.

In nature, a breeding site needs to comply with two requirements: firstly, the banks of the pond should be gently sloping since these frogs tend to avoid steep banks, and secondly, there has to be an overhead cover of shade trees. The second requirement

is merely to make sure that the sometimes very small puddle does not dry out during the development of the larvae, but this is not an immediate risk within the confines of a terrarium. The first requirement is something that should be taken into consideration. Like most tree frogs, *Smilisca* is not very well adapted to climbing steep or sandy riverbanks so make sure that there are sufficient possibilities for the frogs to easily enter and leave the water.

Masked Tree Frog (*Smilisca phaeota*), female. Note the light throat.

Photo: T. Leenders

FOOD

These frogs thrive on a diet of all kind of invertebrates: crickets, flies, moths, almost anything is eaten without problems. Large individuals, such as adult *S. baudinii*, have an almost insatiable appetite and can also be fed with pink baby mice on occasion. *Smilisca baudinii*'s impressive appetite is something that should be taken into consideration when choosing other animals to inhabit the same terrarium. Don't pick any animals that are a lot smaller, because they will be just another addition to the tree frog's diet. It is generally not recommended to keep different species of animals together in the same terrarium.

BREEDING *SMILISCA PHAEOTA* AND *SMILISCA BAUDINII* IN CAPTIVITY

Masked Tree Frog (*Smilisca phaeota*), sleeping on a wild ginger (*Costus* sp.).

Photo: T. Leenders

Smilisca phaeota and *S. baudinii* can be stimulated to breed by imitating a heavy downpour. The best way to achieve this is to keep the terrarium relatively dry for a few weeks. Then, spraying the terrarium for half an hour after the lights are out will usually do the trick. It is hard not to notice whether the males are ready to mate as the volume at which these frogs call is very impressive for an animal of that size. When the female is receptive, the pair can be seen shortly after floating in the water in amplexus.

Eggs should be transferred to a separate aquarium where the larvae will be reared. Within a few hours these eggs develop into free swimming larvae.

In captivity the development of the larvae is extremely fast. Depending on the temperature at which the larvae are kept (I keep them at approximately 26°C) they metamorphose in three to four weeks. The larvae can be fed perfectly well with fish food (pellets) or dry dog food. It is essential that the water in the aquarium is kept clean as poor hygiene will result in high losses in the larvae. For the rest, rearing the larvae is virtually problem-free. Once the tadpoles are almost ready to venture out onto land, a piece of tree fern stem should be put into the aquarium so the larvae can leave the water. This way it is easy to collect the little frogs and transfer them to a terrarium (not with the parents !). Newly metamorphosed froglets measure between 15-19 mm. They can be fed *Drosophila* for the first few weeks, but they grow quickly (some frogs already measure over 50 mm after only two months) and will soon take all sorts of insects. When all is well they will reach maturity after about 10 months.

Rocky river in Costa Rica, home to stream-breeding *Smilisca sordida*.

Photo: T. Leenders

CONCLUSION

It is hard to find anything not to like about these attractive frogs. *Smilisca phaeota* and *S. baudinii* are easy to keep, easy to breed, and are active and visible inhabitants of any rainforest terrarium. The only problem that comes to mind at the moment is their fairly loud call. Once these frogs get going, it can be a slight issue in a residential area. However, in the wild these distinctive vocalisations are just the thing that ensures that you can see these frogs at their best.

SUMMARY

Central America is home to six species of tree frogs of the genus *Smilisca*. Members of this genus can be divided into two groups: species that breed in temporary ponds, and species that only breed in streams. The two species that are most commonly encountered and are the easiest to maintain in captivity, *S. baudinii* and *S. phaeota*, are discussed in more detail. Because of their precarious reproductive strategy, the larvae of these frogs develop extremely rapidly and tadpoles may complete metamorphosis within one month after hatching.

Flooded pasture in Nicaragua. *Smilisca baudinii* and *Smilisca phaeota* use temporary ponds like these.

Photo: T. Leenders

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